

Phytochemical Evaluation of Ethnobotanically Selected Medicinal Plants of Mardan, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Phytochemical and ethnomedicinal study of 27 medicinal plants belonging to different families were carried out. In this study the qualitative analysis of 27 important medicinal plants collected from different sites of Mardan Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan was reported. Different phytochemicals like alkaloids, flavonoids, tannin, terpenoids, anthraquinones, cardiac glycosides, fixed oil and fates, carbohydrates and saponin were analyzed in the specific part of the plant which are being used by the locals as medicine. All the constituents were present differentially in different plants, sixteen plants possess alkaloid, twenty five have flavonoids, twenty plants possess terpenoids, eighteen plants have tannin, eight have anthraquinones, eleven have cardiac glycosides, eight showed fixed oils and fate, and twenty one possess carbohydrates and nineteen plants showed saponin. Ethno medicinal survey of these plants showed that ranging from ear infections, respiratory to urinary diseases, jaundice, diabetes, skin diseases are treated. This study account for the ethnomedicinal importance of the plants by the presence of these phytochemicals which make these plants valuable. So these results endorse for future isolation of phytochemicals for pharmacological production.

Keyword: Medicinal plants, Ethnobotany, Phytochemicals..

INTRODUCTION

Plants are natural springs of producing extensive number of bioactive chemical constituents in a most effective way and with specific selectivity. Since the middle of the 19th century, different class of bioactive complexes have been isolated and described. Many of these are used as the active constituents of the modern medication, or as they lead compounds for new drugs discovery [15]. The medicinal plants are useful for remedial as well as for curing of human diseases because of the occurrence of phytochemical constituents. Phytochemicals are naturally occurring in the medicinal plants, leaves, vegetables and roots that have defense mechanism and protect from various diseases [18]. Plant yields have been part of phytomedicines since time long-established. This can be derivative from barks, leaves, flowers, roots, fruits, seeds. Knowledge of the chemical constituents of plants is desirable because such information will be value for production of complex chemical affluences [19]. Terpenoids display various vital pharmacological activities i.e., anti-inflammatory, anticancer, anti-malarial, inhibition of cholesterol synthesis, anti-viral and anti-bacterial activities [12]. Alkaloids are key in medicines and constitute most of the valued drugs. They have biological effect on animals [7]. Phytochemicals are assembled into two main sets namely primary and secondary. The primary consist of amino acids, proteins, sugars, etc. and the secondary comprises the alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, and saponine. Majority of the phytochemicals have been known to

endure valuable therapeutic actions such as insecticidal, antibacterials, antimalirials, anticonstipative. So the plants finds their medicinal value because of their phytochemical constituents they contain [10].

Ethnobotanically various supplies of *acacia. modesta* are used in the local system of medicine for the treatment of several diseases comprising sketo-muscular problems, to comfort backache for women after delivery, and chronic stomach disorders, since time immemorial. *A. nilotica* is locally used for astringent, emollient, liver tonic, antipyretic and antiasthmatic it is used by traditional healers of different regions of Chhattisgarh in treatment of various cancer types of mouth, bone and skinallium sativum as condiment, antidiabetic, bronchiodilator. *Allium cepa l as* antidiabetic, cough, and for skin diseases, expectorant, carminative. *Ailanthus altissima (mill) swingle* used as anthelmintics, for curing dysentery and diarrhea, urticarias, *amaranthus caudatus l* as purifying blood, diuretic, diuretic; *asparagus filicinus* diarrhea and dysentery; *calotropis procera* asthma, cholera, earache ; *adiantum venustum don*. Fever, cough; *cynodon dactylon* external bleeding, nose & urinary bleeding, jaundice; *chenopodium ambrosioides* backache, motions; *cannabis sativa* antispasmodic, narcotic; *cuscuta reflexa* scabies, eczema and inducing sterility [2, 3, 14, 16, 21]

The principal objective of this research work to document the local medicinal knowledge about plants and to test the selected

medicinal plants for different phytochemicals which are using by the locals as healing and curing agents.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample collection

Medicinal plants were collected locally from the farm lands of mardan area (Pakistan). The plants were used for the purpose of their phytochemical analysis. The plants collected were identified botanically in Department of Botany UCS, Shankar, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan. The medicinally used parts of the selected plants were used for phytochemical analysis. Plant species selected during present investigation were given in [Table.1](#) along their local uses.

Test for alkaloids

The alcoholic extract was evaporated to dryness and the residue was heated on a boiling water bath with 2% hydrochloric acid. After cooling, the mixture was filtered and treated with a few drops of Mayer's reagent. The samples were then observed for the presence of turbidity or yellow precipitation [8].

Test for flavonoids

0.5 g of the methanolic plant extract was shaken with petroleum ether to remove the fatty materials (lipid layer). The defatted residue was dissolved in 20 ml of 80% ethanol and filtered. 3 ml of the filtrate was mixed with 4 ml of 1% potassium hydroxide in a test tube and the colour was observed. A dark yellow colour indicated the presence of flavonoids [17].

Test for terpenoids

5 ml of each plant extract was mixed in 2 ml of chloroform followed by the careful addition of 3 ml concentrated (H₂SO₄). A layer of the reddish brown coloration was formed, results for the presence of terpenoids [17].

Test for tannin

To 0.5 ml of extract solution 1 ml of water and 1 - 2 drops of ferric chloride solution was added. Blue color was observed for Gallic tannins and green black for catecholic tannins [11].

Test for anthraquinones

1.0 g of ethanolic plant extract was boiled in 6 ml of 1% HCl and filtered. The filtrate was shaken with 5 ml benzene and the benzene layer was removed. 10% nh₄oh was added and the colour in the alkaline phase was observed. Formation of pink/violet or red colour indicated the presence of anthraquinones [17].

Test for cardiac glycosides

Keller kiliani test –the extract [50mg] was dissolved in distilled water and then filtered. To 2 ml of filtrate 1ml of glacial acetic acid and a drop of ferric chloride and a drop of concentrated sulfuric acid was added. Green blue color to upper layer and reddish brown color at the junction of two layers indicates the presence of cardiac glycosides [5].

Test for fixed oil and fats

Spot test-a small quantity of extract was pressed between two filter papers. Oil stain on the paper indicates the presence of fixed oils [5].

Test for carbohydrates

Few drops of molisch's reagent was added to each of the portion dissolved in distilled water, this was then followed by addition of 1 ml of conc. H₂so₄ by the side of the test tube. The mixture was then allowed to stand for two minutes and then diluted with 5 ml of distilled water. Formation of a red or dull violet colour at the interphase of the two layers was a positive test [17].

Test for saponine

One gram of each portion was boiled with 5 ml of distilled water, filtered. To the filtrate, about 3ml of distilled water was further added and shaken vigorously for about 5 minutes. Frothing which persisted on warming was taken as an evidence for the presence of saponins [17].

Table 1. List of medicinal plants with their part used and disease treated

S.no.	Botanical name	Parts used	Disease treated
1.	<i>Acacia modesta wall.</i>	Gum	Backache, chronic stomach disorders
2.	<i>Acacia nilotica (l.)Delile.</i>	Gum	Earache, astringent, emollient, liver tonic, antipyretic and antiasthmatic
3.	<i>Albizia lebbeck benth.</i>	Bark	Astringent, tonic, purifies blood
4.	<i>Allium sativum l.</i>	Bulb	Antidiabetic, bronchiodilator, expectorant, carminative
5.	<i>Allium cepa l.</i>	Bulb	Antibiabetic, cough, expectorant, Carminative
6.	<i>Amaranthus viridus l.</i>	Whole	Laxative, abscesses, boils
7.	<i>Ailanthus altissima (mill) swingle</i>	Bark	Dysentery, diarrhea anthelmintics, urtcarias
8.	<i>Amaranthus caudatus l.</i>	Whole plant	Emollients, purifying blood, diuretic, diuretic
9.	<i>Asparagus filicinus bunch.ham.ex d.don</i>	Leaves	Diarrhea and dysentery
10	<i>Adiantum venustum don.</i>	Fronds	Expectorant, emetic, Diuretic
11	<i>Chrozophora tinctoria (linn.)Raffin.</i>	Whole plant	Emetic and cathartic
12	<i>Cynodon dactylon (l.) Pers.</i>	Whole plant	External bleeding, nose & urinary bleeding, jaundice
13	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides l.</i>	Whole plant	Backache, motions
14	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Leaves	Antispasmodic, narcotic

15	<i>Cuscuta reflexa roxb.</i>	Leaves	Scabies, eczema and inducing sterility
16	<i>Calotropis procera (wild.) R.br.</i>	Roots	Asthma, cholera, earache,
17	<i>Chenopodium album l.</i>	Whole plant	Laxative, liver disorder
18	<i>Dalbergia sissoo roxb.</i>	Fruit	Stimulant, astringent
19	<i>Diospyrus lotus stewart</i>	Fruit	Cough, laxative
20	<i>Dodonaea viscosa(l.)Jacq.</i>	Seeds	Swelling, joints pain, boils
21	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia l.</i>	Whole plant	Eczema
22	<i>Euphorbia hirta linn.</i>	Whole plant	Ring worm
23	<i>Eucalyptus lanceolatus l</i>	Leaves	Astringent , as antiseptic
24	<i>Equisetum arvense linn.</i>	Whole plant	Diuretic,
25	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Fruit	Measles, dysentery, bladder problems and verrucas
26	<i>Ficus palmata forssk;</i>	Fruit	Stomachic carminative and diarrhea
27	<i>Vitis venifera l.</i>	Fruit	Laxative

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present work was undertaken to study different parts of 27 medicinal plants that are used locally for treating different diseases (Table.1). These medicinal plants with their different parts used were analyzed phytochemically for alkaloid, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannin, anthraquinones, cardiac glycosides, fixed oil and fats, carbohydrates and saponins (Table 2).

Table 2. Presence and absence of phytochemical in selected medicinal plants

S.no.	Botanical name	Parts used	Alkaloids	Flavonoids	Terpenoids	Tannin	Anthraquinone	Cardiac glycosides	Fixed oil and fats	Carbohydrates	Saponine
1.	<i>Acacia modesta wall.</i>	Gum	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+
2.	<i>Acacia nilotica (l.)Delile.</i>	Gum	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
3.	<i>Albizia lebbbeck benth.</i>	Bark	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+
4.	<i>Allium sativum l.</i>	Bulb	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
5.	<i>Allium cepa l.</i>	Bulb	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
6.	<i>Amaranthus viridus l.</i>	Whole	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+
7.	<i>Ailanthus altissima (mill) swingle</i>	Bark	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-
8.	<i>Amaranthus caudatus l.</i>	Whole plant	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-
9.	<i>Asparagus filicinus bunch.ham.ex d.don</i>	Leaves	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
10.	<i>Adiantum venustum don.</i>	Fronds	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
11.	<i>Chrozophora tinctoria (linn.)Raffin.</i>	Whole plant	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+
12.	<i>Cynodon dactylon (l.) Pers.</i>	Whole plant	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
13.	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides l.</i>	Whole plant	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-
14.	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Leaves	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-
15.	<i>Cuscuta reflexa roxb.</i>	Leaves	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+
16.	<i>Calotropis procera (wild.) R.br.</i>	Roots	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
17.	<i>Chenopodium album l.</i>	Whole plant	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
18.	<i>Dalbergia sissoo roxb.</i>	Fruit	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-

19.	<i>Diospyrus lotus stewart</i>	Fruit	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
20.	<i>Dodonaea viscosa(l.)Jacq.</i>	Seeds	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
21.	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia l.</i>	Whole plant	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
22.	<i>Euphorbia hirta linn.</i>	Whole plant	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+
23.	<i>Eucalyptus lanceolatus l</i>	Leaves	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
24.	<i>Equisetum arvense linn.</i>	Whole plant	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
25.	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Fruit	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
26.	<i>Ficus palmata forssk;</i>	Fruit	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
27.	<i>Vitis venifera l.</i>	Fruit	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+

Among the plants studied here sixteen plants possess alkaloid, twenty five have flavonoids, twenty plants possess terpenoids, eighteen plants have tannin, eight have anthraquinones, eleven have cardiac glycosides, eight showed fixed oils and fate, twenty one possess carbohydrates and nineteen plants showed saponine (Table 3).

Table 3. Number of plants having different phytochemicals

Phytochemical	16
Alkaloids	25
Flavonoids	20
Terpenoids	18
Anthraquinones	8
Cardiac glycosides	11
Fixed oil and fats	8
Carbohydrates	21
Saponine	19

The selected 27 medicinal plants are rich in different phytochemicals because of which they have pronounced effect on specific disease. Tannins are said to be responsible for antimicrobial properties in various plants [4]. Plants with cardiac glycosides, are used in the treatment of congestive heart failure and cardiac arrhythmias. Flavonoids show anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and anti-cancer activity. Saponins have antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory activities. It is also known to have antifungal properties [1]. Langer [11] studied alkaloids, flavonoids and tannins in many plants and found that these chemical constituents were found in sufficient amount among the studied plants. Hadi, and Bremner [9] reported alkaloids in 100 plant species which showed 37% result.

The present study not only document the ethnobotanical uses of various plants but also regarding the qualitative phytochemical analysis of the selected medicinal plants is in agreement with the previous findings of the various researchers.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the present study that plants under investigations showed various bioactive compounds especially alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, saponins and cardiac glycosides. The presence of these bioactive compounds explains its diverse traditional usage in the treatment of numerous diseases and these plant can be subjected for isolation of novel compounds to treat various diseases.

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